

Some novel 2-methyl-3-(1'3'4'-thiadiazoyl)-4-(3H)quinazolinones with anticonvulsant and CNS depressant activity

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Abstract : A series comprising six novel 2-methyl-3-(1'3'4'-thiadiazoyl)-4(3H)quinazolinones have been synthesized by condensing different 2-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazoles with 2-methyl benzoxazin-2-one and evaluated for anticonvulsant and CNS depressant activity. Compound 5f exhibited both anticonvulsant and CNS depressant activity.

Keywords : Quinazolinone, thiadiazoles, methaqualone.

Epilepsy is a chronic and often-progressive disorder characterized by the periodic and unpredictable occurrence of epileptic seizures, which are caused by an abnormal discharge of cerebral neurons¹. We have earlier reported the CNS depressant² and antihistaminic effect³ showed by 1,3,4-thiadiazoles. Apart from methaqualone (2-methyl-3-*o*-tolyl-4(3H)quinazolinone) being an established anticonvulsant there are reports of certain other substituted 4(3H)quinazolinones as anticonvulsants^{4,5}. The present communication deals with methaqualone analogues in which aryl group at position 3 has been replaced with substituted 1,3,4-thiadiazoles.

Results and discussion

All the synthesized compounds (5a-f) were characterized on the basis of nitrogen analysis. IR and NMR spectra were consistent with the assigned structure (Table 1). All the synthesized compounds showed CNS depressant activity particularly compounds 5d and 5f. Among the prepared series electronegative substituent placed *para* to the aryl ring showed better activity. Results indicate that electron rich moiety at *para* increases while electron deficient moiety decreases both anticonvulsant and CNS depressant activity. In general aromatic compounds were found to be more potent than their aliphatic counterparts.

Table 1. Molecular formula, nitrogen estimation, melting point, IR and NMR study of the synthesised molecules

Compd.	R	Mol. formula	% Nitrogen Calcd. (Found)	m.p. (°C)	IR (KBr)	¹³ C NMR (benzene (cm ⁻¹)+ methanol) (δ ppm)
5a	CH ₃ 1''	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₄ SO	21.7 (20.87)	168-170	C-H str (aro)- 3020, C-H def 4H atom-760, C-H str (alkyl)-2850, C-H def (alkyl)-1450, C=C str-1650, C=O str-1690, C-N str- 1310, C=N str- 1630, C-S str-650	C-11 (13.5), C-1'' (21), C-8 (118.5), C-6 (121), C-9 (128), C-5 (130), C-7 (133.7), C-10 (142), C-5' (140), C-2 (158), C-5 (168), C-4 (170)

Table-1 (contd.)

5b	$\text{CH}_2 \text{ CH}_2 \text{ CH}_3$ 1'' 2'' 3''	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4\text{SO}$	19.5 (18.95)	158–160	C-H str (aro)-3020, C-H def 4H atom- 760, C-H str (alkyl)- 2850, C-H def (alkyl)- 1450, C=C str- 1650, C=O str- 1690, C-N str-1310, C=N str-1630, C-S str-650	C-11 (13.5), C-1'' (21), C-8 (118.5), C-6 (121), C-9 (128), C-5 (130), C-7 (133.7), C-10 (142), C-5' (140), C-2 (158), C-5 (168), C-4 (170), C-2'' (32.1), C-3'' (22.5)
5c	$\text{CH}_2 \text{ CH}_2 \text{ CH}_2 \text{ CH}_3$ 1'' 2'' 3'' 4''	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{SO}$	18.6 (18.0)	160–162	C-H str (aro)-3020, C-H def 4H atom- 760, C-H str (alkyl)- 2850, C-H def (alkyl)- 1450, C=C str-1650, C=O str-1690, C-N str-1310, C=N str- 1630, C-S str-650	C-11 (13.5), C-1'' (21), C-8 (118.5), C-6 (121), C-9 (128), C-5 (130), C-7 (133.7), C-10 (142), C-5' (140), C-2 (158), C-5 (168), C-4 (170), C-2'' (32.1), C-3'' (22.5), C-4'' (15.0)
5d		$\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{SO}$	17.5 (17.3)	172–174	C-H str (aro)-3020, C-H def 4H atom- 760, C-H str (alkyl)- 2850, C-H def (alkyl)- 1450, C=C str-1650, C=O str-1690, C-N str-1310, C=N str- 1630, C-S str-650, mono substituted phenyl ring-760	C-11 (13.5), C-1'' (21), C-8 (118.5), C-6 (121), C-9 (128), C-5 (130), C-7 (133.7), C-10 (142), C-5' (140), C-2 (158), C-2' (168), C-4 (170), C-1'' (134), C-2'' and C-6'' (130.3), C-3'' and C-5'' (138.2), C-4'' (127.7)
5e		$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{SO}$	16.7 (16.1)	180–182	C-H str (aro)-3020, C-H def 4H atom- 760, C-H str (alkyl)- 2850, C-H def (alkyl)- 1450, C=C str-1650, C=O str-1690, C-N str-1310, C=N str- 1630, C-S str-650, 1,4-substituted phenyl ring 830- 815	C-11 (13.5), C-1'' (21), C-8 (118.5), C-6 (121), C-9 (128), C-5 (130), C-7 (133.7), C-10 (142), C-5' (140), C-2 (158), C-2' (168), C-4 (170), C-1'' (134), C-2'' and C-6'' (130.3), C-3'' and C-5'' (138.2), C-4'' (127.7), C-7'' (21.5)

Note

Table-1 (contd)

5f		C ₁₇ H ₉ N ₄ SO	15.7 (15.0)	189-190	C-H str (aro)-3020, C-H def 4H atom- 760, C-H str (alkyl)- 2850, C-H def (alkyl)- 1450, C=C str-1650, C=O str-1690, C-N str-1310, C=N str- 1630, C-S str-650, 1,4-substituted phenyl ring 830-815	C-11 (13 5), C-1'' (21), C-8 (118.5), C-6 (121), C-9 (128), C-5 (130), C-7 (133 7), C-10 (142), C-5' (140), C-2 (158), C-2' (168), C-4 (170), C-1'' (134), C-2'' and C-6'' (130 3), C-3'' and C-5'' (138 2), C-4' (132 4)
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Aromaticity imparts some activity enhancing property to the compounds. No reported compound showed activity at stuper phase which is true for standard drug also. Lipophilic compounds showed better anticonvulsant and CNS depressant activity (5d, 5e, 5f). After anticonvulsant screening all the animals recovered and not a single death occurred. Anticonvulsant activities were observed for all the compounds. Compound 5f, showed definite decrease in all phases of convulsion except flexor phase.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open glass capillary and are uncorrected. The purity was checked by TLC using silica gel G as stationary phase and hexane : ethanol : chloroform (1 : 3 : 6) as mobile phase. The structures of the synthesized compounds were elucidated by using Shimadzu 470 IR spectrophotometer in KBr phase (ν_{\max} in cm^{-1}). ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on C¹³ Avance Bruker 300 MHz spectrometer. Nitrogen analysis was obtained from RSIC, CDRI, Lucknow.

Synthesis :

Synthesis of 2-amino-5-aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (3a) : The original procedure of Ranga Rao and Srinivasan⁵ as modified and used. Aromatic aldehyde (0.2 mol) in warm alcohol (300 ml) was added to a solution of thiosemicarbazide (0.2 mol) in hot water (300 ml) was mixed slowly with continuous stirring. The product, which separated, were filtered off and recrystallised from 50% aqueous ethanol. 2a, R = H, yield 92%, m.p. 159-160 °C

(lit.158-160 °C); 2b, R = CH₃, 95%, 162 °C (160-161 °C); 2c, R = Cl, 90%, 207-209 °C (209-210.5 °C).

Thiosemicarbazone (2) (0.05 mol) was suspended in 300 ml distilled water in a 1000 ml beaker. Ferric chloride (0.15 mol) in 300 ml distilled water was added to it. The contents were heated and maintained at 80-90° for an hour. Then it was filtered hot. A mixture of citric acid (0.11 mol) and sodium citrate (0.05 mol) was added to the solution and stirred. After cooling the whole solution was taken in a bigger vessel (to account for the increase in volume) and neutralized with 10% aqueous ammonia. The precipitate which separated out was filtered and recrystallised from 25% aqueous ethanol except 3a₃ which was recrystallised from 50% ethanol. 3a₁, R = H, yield 65%, m.p. 224-225 °C (lit. 224 °C); 3a₂, R = CH₃, 62%, 214-215 °C (215-216 °C); 3a₃, R = Cl, 70%, 227-229 °C (229-230 °C).

*Synthesis of 2-amino-5-alkyl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (3b)*⁷ : Required fatty acid (0.15 mol), concentrated sulphuric acid (AnalaR, sp. gr. 1.84, 25 mL) and thiosemicarbazide (0.125 mol) were slowly heated to 80-90° on a thermostatically controlled water bath for 7 h after cooling the content was poured on crushed ice. The acid was neutralized with the help of 10% ammonia solution. The crude precipitate which got separated was filtered and washed several times with distilled water and dried. Final product were recrystallised from hot water except 3b₃, which was recrystallised from 50% ethanol. 3b₁, R = CH₃, yield 65%, m.p. 231 °C (lit. 232-233

$^{\circ}\text{C}$); $3b_2$, $R = C_3H_7$, 85%, 204–205 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (205 $^{\circ}\text{C}$); $3b_3$, $R = C_4H_9$, 80%, 195 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (195–196 $^{\circ}\text{C}$).

Scheme 1. Synthetic pathway for the synthesis of substituted-1,3,4-thiadiazol

Synthesis of the title compounds (5a-f)⁸: A mixture of recrystallised anthranilic acid (0.01 mol), acetic anhydride (0.02 mol) and acetic acid (0.01 mol) were taken in round-bottomed flask and refluxed for 4 h the acetic acid together with acetic anhydride was distilled off under reduced pressure. The compound 3(a and b) (0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid was added to the benzoxazine-4-one (4) slowly and refluxed 4–5 h. The mixture so obtained was added to crushed ice and separated precipitate was filtered off. Recrystallisation was carried out from 25% aqueous ethanol except (5a) with hot water, (5f) with 50% ethanol, (5b) and (5c) with ethanol.

Pharmacological evaluation :

Lethal dose (LD₅₀) : Albino mice (20–25 g) were divided into groups of five animals each. These were ad-

Scheme 2. Synthetic pathway for the synthesis of title compounds (5a-f).

ministered 215, 464, 1000 mg/kg and the observations made for mortality up to 24 h. The lethal doses were then taken from the Horn's Table⁹.

CNS depressant activity¹⁰ : Albino mice of either sex weighing 25–35 g were divided into the groups of five animals each. Oral suspensions of the drug (100 mg/kg) in 3% PVP (polyvinyl pyrrolidone) were given to animals of all groups. After 30 min interval the animals of the groups were kept in the actophotometer and reading for 5 min time interval noted (Table 2). The meter readings were compared with the control groups and the groups that received standard drug (chlorpromazine, 3 mg/kg i.p.).

Anticonvulsant activity¹¹ : Albino mice of either sex (150–200 g) were used for anticonvulsant activity against Maximal Electro Shock (MES) induced seizures. Animals were divided into groups of five animals each. They were given the oral suspension of the drug (100 mg/kg). The standard drug used for the presence study was diphenyl hydantoin 25 mg/kg by i.p. route. The control group received only PVP suspension. Reading was recorded after 30 min of drug administration (Table 3).

Seizure was produced in rats by “Techno” convulsio-meter by delivering a current of 150 mA through the corneal electrodes for a period of 0.2 s. The animals were placed on the table and its head was fixed. The electrodes were dipped in normal saline and placed gently on the cornea. The animals were observed for the toxic phase, flexor phase (towards the upper extremities), extensor phase (extension of the lower extremities), clonic phase (intermediate jerking of the limbs), stupor (unconsciousness) and at last recovery or death. Time for each phase was noted by a stopwatch. The LD₅₀ of the synthesized compounds was found to be > 2150 mg/kg. Thus, the synthesized compounds were safe and nontoxic.

Note

Table 2. CNS depressant activity of the compounds (5a-f)

Compd	R	CNS depressant activity in 5 min ^a	LD ₅₀ (mg/kg)
5a	CH ₃	454	>2150
5b	C ₃ H ₇	433	>2150
5c	C ₄ H ₉	440	>2150
5d		365	>2150
5e		449	>2150
5f		350	>2150
Control	-	498	>2150
Standard (chlorpromazine)	-	310	>2150

^aActophotometer reading

Table 3. Anticonvulsant activity of the compounds (5a-f)

Compd	Time (s) in various phases of convulsion				
	Flexion (mean ± SE)	Extensor (mean ± SE)	Clonic (mean ± SE)	Stupor (mean ± SE)	Recovery/Death
5a	2 8 ± 0 3	10 4 ± 0 5	3 2 ± 0 5	109 8 ± 0 8	Recovery
5b	2 4 ± 0 2	10 0 ± 0 7	4 4 ± 0 5	102 0 ± 3 2	Recovery
5c	2 4 ± 0 2	10 4 ± 0 7	2 4 ± 0 5	109 8 ± 0 9	Recovery
5d	2 2 ± 0 2	7 0 ± 0 8	3 6 ± 0 5	109 8 ± 2 3	Recovery
5e	2 2 ± 0 3	7 8 ± 0 8	3 4 ± 0 5	109 8 ± 1 4	Recovery
5f	2 6 ± 0 3	5 2 ± 0 7	1 2 ± 0 5	109 8 ± 1 9	Recovery
Control	2 4 ± 0 2	12 4 ± 0 7	5 8 ± 0 5	109 8 ± 2 3	Recovery
Standard (diphenyl hydantoin)	Absent	4 0 ± 0 2	0 8 ± 0 5	109 8 ± 1 8	Recovery

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